

Submandibular Intubation as an Airway Management Strategy in Panfacial Fractures: A Case Report

Michele Yoselin, MD*¹, Puri Ambar Lestari²

¹Medical Doctor, EMC Hospital Cikarang, West Java, Indonesia

²Cranio-maxillofacial and Trauma Surgeon, Department of Plastic Reconstructive and Aesthetic Surgery, EMC Hospital Cikarang, West Java, Indonesia

ABSTRACT

Background: Management of the airway in patients with panfacial fractures is challenging. Submandibular intubation is useful as an alternative method to establish safe airway patency with full access to the surgical site without the need for a tracheostomy with its associated risks and complications.

Case: A 16-year-old male suffered craniofacial trauma due to a motorcycle accident with panfacial fractures. The patient's condition required an unobstructed surgical field for occlusion evaluation, intermaxillary fixation, and complex reconstruction. It was decided to use submandibular intubation. The procedure was performed by making a small incision in the submandibular region, diverting the endotracheal tube from the oral cavity to outside the incision, and fixing it to the skin. The surgery went smoothly without intraoperative or postoperative complications.

Intervention and Management: Submandibular intubation was performed by making a small right submandibular incision, redirecting the endotracheal tube through the floor of the mouth, and securing it with sutures, ensuring a clear operative field. The patient tolerated the procedure well and recovered without complications, with smooth healing of the incision site.

Discussion: Recent literature indicates that submandibular intubation provides stable airway access, avoid tracheostomy complications, and facilitates complex reconstruction procedures. This case reinforces the evidence of the effectiveness and safety of this technique in the management of panfacial fractures.

Conclusion: Submandibular intubation is an alternative method for airway management in panfacial fractures. It is safe, effective, and viable strategic option for complex panfacial fractures.

KEYWORDS: Panfacial fractures, Submandibular intubation, Airway management.

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INTRODUCTION

Panfacial fractures in which the three main facial units (frontal, midface and the mandible) are involved are one of the most complex injuries in maxillofacial traumatology. With the increase in traffic accidents, particularly among the younger population, there has been a proportional increase in the occurrence of panfacial fractures. This condition not only causes significant aesthetic deformities but also poses major challenges in airway management, dental occlusion, and facial anatomical reconstruction.^{1,2,3}

Airway management is a crucial initial step in patients with panfacial fractures. Orotracheal intubation often hinders intraoperative evaluation of dental occlusion, while nasotracheal intubation is contraindicated in naso-orbito-ethmoid or cranial base fractures due to the risk of intracranial penetration.³ Tracheostomy, although providing stable airway access, carries the risk of serious complications such as bleeding, tracheal stenosis, fistula, and increased morbidity.^{1,4}

The submandibular approach to intubation was described by Hernández Altemir in 1986, since then it has

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been one of the techniques that compete with orotracheal, Nasotracheal or tracheostomy intubation. This technique is performed by making a small incision in the submandibular region, followed by diverting the endotracheal tube from the oral cavity to the outside through the incision. This method allows for a clearer surgical field without comprising airway stability.^{5,6}

Several studies have known that submandibular intubation has a high success rate with minimal complications. In a systematic literature review, this technique was found to be safe, quick, and effective, with minor complications such as superficial wound infection or scarring rarely reported. Another advantage is the absence of long-term risks associated with tracheostomy.⁷

This case is reported to emphasize the importance of submandibular intubation as an airway management strategy in panfacial fractures requiring complex reconstruction. This report also aims to add clinical evidence regarding the safety and effectiveness of this technique, especially in young patients with precise reconstruction needs.

CASE DESCRIPTION

A 16-year-old male patient was admitted to the emergency room after a motorcycle accident with craniofacial trauma. The patient was fully conscious (GCS 15), with bilateral periorbital oedema, mid-lower face oedema, epistaxis, malocclusion, and step-off deformity of the mandible. A CT scan showed panfacial fractures including bilateral mandibular angle fractures, complex right zygomaticomaxillary fractures, and naso-orbito-ethmoid fractures (Figure 1).

Figure 1. CT scan of panfacial fractures (a) complex right zygomaticomaxillary fractures, (b,c) bilateral mandibular angle fractures, and naso-orbito-ethmoid fractures.

INTERVENTION AND MANAGEMENT

Management of panfacial fractures becomes challenging when a clear surgical field is needed to achieve precise occlusion, perform intermaxillary fixation, fracture reduction, and complex midface reconstruction in a single surgical session. Considering the need for a clear surgical field for reconstruction and occlusion evaluation, submandibular intubation was decided upon.

Submandibular intubation serves as an alternative method of airway management that bypasses the standard anatomical routes used in orotracheal intubation. The procedure began with an initial orotracheal intubation (Figure 2), then a 2 cm skin incision was made in the right

submandibular region. Through this incision, blunt dissection was carried out through the platysma and mylohyoid muscles until the oral cavity was reached. The pilot balloon was delivered first, followed by the proximal end of the endotracheal tube, which was then brought out through the incision. The tube was reconnected to the circuit and secured externally with silk sutures (Figure 3), and surgical procedures including intermaxillary fixation, reduction, and fixation of fractures proceeded without airway interference.

The patient remained stable throughout the procedure, with no episodes of desaturation or abnormal bleeding. At the end of surgery, the tube was redirected intraorally and the submandibular incision closed with absorbable sutures. Postoperatively, the patient showed good recovery, with the submandibular wound healing without infection or significant scarring.

Figure 2. Orotracheal intubation

Figure 3. Submandibular intubation secured externally with silk sutures

DISCUSSION

Panfacial fractures are one of the most complex forms of facial trauma because they involve simultaneous fractures of the mandible, maxilla, zygomatic bone, and naso-orbito-ethmoid complex.^{1,2,3} This case demonstrates that submandibular intubation can be an optimal solution in airway management for panfacial fractures. As reported by Altemir (1986), this technique provides the advantage of wider surgical access without compromising airway stability.^{3,6} Modern literature supports the use of this technique. Submandibular intubation reduces the risk of serious complications that often occur with tracheostomy and allows for more precise evaluation of occlusion compared to orotracheal intubation.^{4,7,8} In a review by Roig et al. (2024), submandibular intubation was reported to have a success rate of 100% with minor complications that can be managed conservatively.¹ Reported complications include superficial wound infection, minimal scarring, or submandibular and sublingual glands or duct injury, and mucocele formation.^{1,8}

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Another advantage is that the procedure is relatively short, usually taking only about 6-10 minutes, so it does not significantly increase the duration of anaesthesia (Yuan et al., 2024).^{6,9} This is consistent with our case, in which the total tube transfer time was approximately 10 minutes without hemodynamic or respiratory disturbances. It is also important to note that submandibular intubation is not intended for long-term use. This technique should be used in reconstructive procedures that require a safe intraoperative airway, but patients still require extubation immediately after surgery or an alternative if long-term ventilation is necessary.^{3,10}

This case adds clinical evidence that submandibular intubation is a safe, effective, and viable option, particularly in young patients with complex facial reconstruction needs. This reinforces recommendations in the literature that this technique should be considered as an alternative standard alongside tracheostomy.

CONCLUSIONS

Submandibular intubation is a safe, rapid, and effective technique for airway management in cases of panfacial fractures. This case demonstrates the advantages of this technique in providing an optimal surgical field, avoiding tracheostomy complications, allowing complex reconstruction to proceed smoothly, and provides superior aesthetic outcomes.

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